

Microwave-assisted synthesis and evaluation of indole derivatives as potential anthelmintic agents

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An efficient method is developed and exploited for the synthesis of indole derivatives via microwave-assisted technology. By considering the advantage microwave synthesis in terms of high efficient energy, indole derivatives are prepared. In the current study, the Schiff's bases are first synthesized by reaction of 1*H*-indole-2,3-dione (isatin) with various substituted anilines in presence of acetic acid under microwave irradiation. Then the Mannich bases are produced by condensation of Schiff bases with different secondary amines in the presence of formaldehyde. The newly synthesized compounds are characterized by TLC report and spectral data followed by evaluation for anthelmintic activity against *Pheretima posthuma*. Albendazole is used as standard drug for comparative study. The titled compounds are screened for anthelmintic activity at the concentration of 10, 20 and 50 mg/ml. The anthelmintic effect of standard drug Albendazole is also evaluated at 10 mg/ml. The results of present study indicate that some of the tested compounds exhibit significant anthelmintic activity in dose dependent manner.

Keywords: Anthelmintic agents, indole, Mannich bases, microwave, Schiff bases, synthesis.

Introduction

The chemistry of heterocyclic scaffolds play key role in the area of drug research. Among nitrogen containing heterocyclic compounds, indole derivatives exhibit promising biological activities such as antibacterial, antifungal, anticancer, anticonvulsant, anti-tubercular, anti-Alzheimer, analgesic, antiviral and anti-inflammatory etc.^{1,2}. Isatin (1,3-dihydro-2*H*-indol-2-one) is an endogenous compound with wide range of biological activities. Isatin was first prepared by Erdman and Laurent in 1841 as a product from the oxidation of indigo by nitric and chromic acids³. Schiff and Mannich bases of isatin also represent the most important classes of organic compounds due to their diverse pharmacological activities^{4,5}.

On the other hand, the microwave technology has several advantages as compared to traditional or conventional methods of synthesis. The reduced reaction times, eco-friendly and better product yields of microwave synthesis attract to carry out the synthesis. In the present study, both

the microwave technique as well as conventional methods is followed to prepare indole derivatives^{6,7}.

Traditionally, organic reactions are carried out by using external heat source such as an oil bath, water bath, heating mantle etc. thereby heat is transferred by conductance. This process of heating is comparatively slow and inefficient for transferring energy into the reaction medium because it depends on the thermal conductivity of the various reacting materials that must be penetrated, and results in the temperature of the reaction vessel being higher than that of the reaction mixture^{8,9}. By contrast, microwave irradiation produces efficient internal heating by direct coupling of microwave energy with the polar molecules (for example, solvents, reagents and catalysts) that are present in the reaction mixture¹⁰.

Microwave synthesis is generally based on the efficient heating of reacting materials by microwave dielectric heating effects¹¹. Microwave dielectric heating depends on the

ability of a specific substance to absorb microwave energy and convert it into heat. Microwave irradiation triggers heating to carry out the chemical reaction by two main mechanisms such as dipolar polarization and ionic conduction. Whereas the dipoles in the reaction mixture (for example, the polar solvent molecules) are involved in the dipolar polarization effect, the charged particles in a sample (usually ions) are affected by ionic conduction¹².

Microwave-assisted heating has been shown to be an invaluable technology in synthesis, since it can often dramatically reduce reaction times, typically from days or hours to minutes or even seconds. It can also provide pure products in quantitative yield and selectivity. When solvent is used, the reaction condition must be carefully controlled or a special apparatus should be used, due to the danger of using organic solvents in microwave irradiation because of their low boiling points and high vapor pressure^{13,14}.

Helminth infections are among the most common infections in humans, upsetting a massive population of the world. The World Health Organization estimates that more than two billions of people are in parasitic worm infections. These infections are the most common health problems in India and also in other developing countries^{15,16}. There are two important types of worm infections, those in which the worms live in the host alimentary canal and those in which the worms live in other tissues of the host body. Common examples of worms are the tape worm, intestinal round worm, trematodes or flukes, tissue round worm, etc. Various diseases caused by helminthes are ascariasis, trichirians, hook worm and tape worm infection, thread worm infection, schistosomiasis, giardial infection. The gastro-intestinal helminthes become resistant to currently available anthelmintic drugs. Anthelmintics are those agents that expel parasitic worms (helminthes) from the body, by either stunning or killing them. To overcome the development of drug resistance, it is very important to synthesize a new class of compounds possessing different chemical properties to treat helminthes diseases^{17,18}.

Experimental

Materials:

The chemicals and solvents used for the experimental

work were of commercially grade. All the melting points were taken in open capillaries and are uncorrected. The purity of the synthesized compounds was checked by TLC on pre-coated silica gel-aluminum plates (Type 60 F254, Merck, Darmstadt, Germany) and were visualized by exposure to UV-light (254 nm) or iodine vapor for few seconds. The IR spectra of the compounds were recorded on FT-IR Spectrophotometer, model IR Affinity-1 (Shimadzu), using KBr powder and the values are expressed in cm^{-1} . ¹H NMR spectra of the selected compounds were recorded on FT-NMR Spectrometer, model Advance-II (Bruker), (at 400 MHz) using tetramethylsilane (TMS) as an internal standard. The multiplicities of the signals are presented as singlet, doublet, triplet and multiplet etc. The microwave irradiated synthesis was performed in scientific microwave oven, Catalyst System (operating between 140–700 W). All the synthetic reactions were carried out at power level-1, which corresponds to 140 W.

Methods:

Conventional synthesis of Schiff bases of indole derivatives (2a-f):

Equimolar (0.01 mol) quantity of isatin and substituted anilines were dissolved in ethanol (10 mL) and refluxed for 2 h in presence of glacial acetic acid (Scheme 1). In between TLC was checked to confirm the completion of reaction. After completion of reaction, the reaction mixture was kept overnight to get the solid product. The product was filtered, dried and recrystallized from ethanol.

Scheme 1. Synthetic route of the titled compounds (3a-f).

Table 1. Comparative study on yield and reaction time of the synthesized compounds (**2a-f**) by conventional and microwave assisted method

Compd. code	Conventional method			Microwave assisted method		
	Time (h)	Energy (Temp. °C)	Yield (%)	Time (min)	Energy (Power, Watt)	Yield (%)
2a	2	90–100	55	4	140	74
2b	2	90–100	58	5	140	72
2c	2	90–100	56	10	140	83
2d	2	90–100	63	7	140	82
2e	2	90–100	57	6	140	77
2f	3	90–100	53	8	140	82

Microwave assisted synthesis of Schiff bases of indole derivatives (**2a-f**):

The required quantities of above reactants are subjected to microwave irradiation at power level-1 which corresponds to 140 w for 4–10 min. In between TLC was performed to confirm the completion of reaction. After completion of reaction, the reaction mixture was kept overnight to get the solid product. The product was filtered, dried and recrystallized from ethanol.

Synthesis of Mannich bases of indole derivatives (**3a-f**):

Mannich bases of indole derivatives were prepared by condensing equimolar proportions of appropriate Schiff bases, secondary amine and formaldehyde. The reaction mixture was stirred for 1 h at room temperature and then kept overnight under refrigeration to get the solid product. The product was filtered, dried and recrystallized from ethanol. The secondary amine used for the synthesis of Mannich bases are diethyl amine. The mixture of chloroform and ethyl acetate (60:40) is used as mobile phase for TLC study. The physical and spectral data of the synthesized compounds were given in Tables 2 and 3.

Anthelmintic activity:

The anthelmintic activity was performed on *Pheretima posthuma* (Indian earthworm) as it has anatomical and physiological similarity with the intestinal parasites of human beings. The standard drug and test compounds were dissolved in dimethyl formamide (DMF) and the volume was adjusted up to 15 mL with normal saline solution to get the concentration of 10, 20 and 50 mg/ml. Albendazole was used as the standard drug and normal saline was used as control. Both test and standard solutions were poured into the petridishes.

Table 2. TLC report and melting point data of the synthesized compounds (**3a-f**)

Compd. code	X	m.p (°C)	R _f
3a	4-NO ₂	163–165	0.63
3b	4-Cl	154–157	0.68
3c	4-F	152–154	0.60
3d	4-Br	164–167	0.73
3e	4-OH	148–150	0.58
3f	4-OCH ₃	151–154	0.62

Six worms were placed in each petridish. The worms were kept under observation to record the paralysis and dead time at room temperature. Paralysis was said to occur when the worms did not receive even in normal saline and dead should be confirmed by putting motionless worms in 40°C warm water. The time taken by worms to become motionless was noted as paralysis time^{19,20}. The mean lethal time and paralysis time of the earth worms for different test compounds and standard drug are given in Table 4.

Results and discussion

Both conventional and microwave heating method were followed to carry out the synthesis of Schiff bases of indole

Table 3. Characterization data of the titled compounds (**3a-f**)

Compd. code	MF	MW	IR, NMR and Mass
3a	C ₁₉ H ₂₀ N ₄ O ₃	352.38	IR (cm ⁻¹): 1728 (C=O), 1602 (C=N), 1462 (C=C), 1527, 1352 (NO ₂); ¹ H NMR δ (ppm): 0.97–1.15 (t, 6H, N(CH ₂ CH ₃) ₂), 2.50–2.65 (q, 4H, N(CH ₂ CH ₃) ₂), 4.48 (s, 2H, CH ₂), 6.56–7.69 (m, 8H, Ar-H). <i>m/z</i> : 352.38.
3b	C ₁₉ H ₂₀ ClN ₃ O	341.83	IR (cm ⁻¹): 1728 (C=O), 1602 (C=N), 1462 (C=C), 759 (C-Cl); ¹ H NMR δ (ppm): 0.97–1.15 (t, 6H, N(CH ₂ CH ₃) ₂), 2.50–2.65 (q, 4H, N(CH ₂ CH ₃) ₂), 4.48 (s, 2H, CH ₂), 6.56–7.69 (m, 8H, Ar-H). <i>m/z</i> : 342.
3c	C ₁₉ H ₂₀ FN ₃ O	325.38	IR (cm ⁻¹): 1716 (C=O), 1612 (C=N), 1444 (C=C), 1097 (C-F); ¹ H NMR δ (ppm): 1.31 (t, 6H, N(CH ₂ CH ₃) ₂), 2.57 (q, 4H, N(CH ₂ CH ₃) ₂), 3.28 (s, 2H, CH ₂), 6.49–7.91 (m, 8H, Ar-H).
3d	C ₁₉ H ₂₀ BrN ₃ O	386.28	IR (cm ⁻¹): 1728 (C=O), 1602 (C=N), 1462 (C=C), 759 (C-Br); ¹ H NMR δ (ppm): 0.97–1.15 (t, 6H, N(CH ₂ CH ₃) ₂), 2.50–2.65 (q, 4H, N(CH ₂ CH ₃) ₂), 4.48 (s, 2H, CH ₂), 6.56–7.69 (m, 8H, Ar-H).
3e	C ₁₉ H ₂₁ N ₃ O ₂	323.38	IR (cm ⁻¹): 1728 (C=O), 1604 (C=N), 1467 (C=C), 3630 (-OH); ¹ H NMR δ (ppm): 1.05–1.13 (t, 6H, N(CH ₂ CH ₃) ₂), 2.60–2.65 (q, 4H, N(CH ₂ CH ₃) ₂), 4.48 (s, 2H, CH ₂), 4.61 (s, 1H, OH). <i>m/z</i> : 324.
3f	C ₂₀ H ₂₃ N ₃ O ₂	337.41	IR (cm ⁻¹): 1726 (C=O), 1600 (C=N), 1467 (C=C), 1290–1250 (-OCH ₃); ¹ H NMR δ (ppm): 0.97–1.15 (t, 6H, N(CH ₂ CH ₃) ₂), 2.50–2.65 (q, 4H, N(CH ₂ CH ₃) ₂), 4.48 (s, 2H, CH ₂), 3.94 (s, 3H, OCH ₃).

Table 4. Anthelmintic activity of the synthesized Mannich bases (**3a-f**)

Compd.	Concentration (mg/ml)	Time of paralysis	Time of death
		(min)	(min)
		Mean ± SD	Mean ± SD
3a	10	60±0.18	158±0.19
	20	57±0.14	145±0.24
	50	53±0.32	139±0.34
3b	10	48±0.24	134±0.27
	20	41±0.33	128±0.33
	50	37±0.16	115±0.32
3c	10	57±0.39	152±0.17
	20	53±0.34	148±0.43
	50	48±0.24	142±0.21
3d	10	64±0.33	156±0.35
	20	61±0.31	140±0.34
	50	57±0.42	137±0.51
3e	10	66±0.35	165±0.28
	20	63±0.42	143±0.34
	50	60±0.51	140±0.34
3f	10	64±0.19	186±0.29
	20	61±0.35	175±0.21
	50	58±0.25	157±0.36
Control (Normal saline)	–	–	–
Standard (Albendazole)	10	49±0.56	68±0.21
	20	44±0.15	62±0.31
	50	38±0.21	53±0.24

derivatives (**2a-f**). In case of conventional heating method, syntheses of the titled compounds were completed in 2 h where as the reaction was completed within 4–10 min by microwave irradiation method. While considering the yield of the product, it was observed that the yield of the compounds was found to be 53–63% in case of conventional whereas 72–83% by microwave heating method. To optimize the better yield of the products, the effect of various parameters such as microwave energy, irradiation time and molar proportions of the reactants should be considered. So it can be concluded that microwave heating provided high yield with pure product in less reaction time. Comparative study on yield and reaction time of the Schiff bases were included in Table 1.

The *R_f* value is characteristic for each synthesized compounds and the values were found to be in the range of 0.58–0.73 and were presented in Table 2. IR data of compound **3a** showed characteristics absorptions at 1728, 1602, 1462, 1527 and 1352 cm⁻¹ indicating the presence of C=O, C=N, C=C and NO₂ group respectively. The absorption bands at 1728, 1602, 1462 and 759 cm⁻¹ which indicates the presence of C=O, C=N, C=C and C-Cl in case of compound **3b**. Similarly compound **3c** exhibited characteristic peaks at 1716, 1612, 1444, 1097 cm⁻¹ indicates the presence of C=O, C=N, C=C and C-F groups. Whereas compound **3d** displayed IR absorption bands at 1728, 1602, 1462, 759 cm⁻¹ which corre-

sponds the functional groups such as C=O, C=N, C=C and C-Br. In case of compound **3e**, the peaks at 1728, 1604, 1467, 3630 cm^{-1} relied the presence of C=O, C=N, C=C and OH groups. While IR absorption bands of **3f** gave an idea about the presence of C=O, C=N, C=C and $-\text{OCH}_3$ groups which corresponds to 1726, 1600, 1467 and 1290–1250 cm^{-1} respectively. The ^1H NMR spectra of the above synthesized compounds has shown singlet in the region of δ 9.35 to 9.98 corresponding to secondary amino group ($-\text{NH}$). The aromatic protons resonate as multiplet in the region of δ 7.03 to 7.90. The O-H stretching vibration is observed in the region of 3550–3200 cm^{-1} .

After characterization of the synthesized compounds, these were evaluated for their anthelmintic activity by using *Pheretima posthuma* (Indian earthworm) at three different concentrations i.e., 10, 20 and 50 mg/ml. The results of the study were summarized in Table 4 including the activity of standard drug Albendazole. From the experiment, it was observed that the compounds at higher concentrations produced paralytic effect much earlier and the time to death was shorter for the worms. The compound **3a** exhibited the paralysis of worms within 53–60 min while death of the worms was observed at 158–139 min at the test concentrations of 10, 20 and 50 mg/ml respectively. Among the tested compounds, the compound **3b** has taken less time i.e., 48, 41 and 37 min for paralysis of *Pheretima posthuma* similarly the death of worms was observed at 134, 128 and 115 min for the concentration of 10, 20 and 50 mg/ml respectively.

Conclusions

In this present study, some Schiff base of indole derivatives are synthesized by conventional and microwave irradiation method. With the help of microwave synthesis, the yield of product was increased from 54% upto 83% as compared to conventional method. By microwave irradiation, the reactions were completed within 4–10 min and the products were obtained in high yields, which reduce reaction time, formation of byproduct and waste. The microwave assisted synthesis is simple, eco-friendly and can be used as an alternative to the existing conventional heating method. From the results of anthelmintic studies, it was concluded that the tested compounds exhibited significant anthelmintic activities against the test organism *Pheretima posthuma*. Among

the tested compounds, compound substituted with electron withdrawing group on indole nucleus showed promising anthelmintic activities. It can be concluded that the reproducibility and speed of microwave assisted synthesis would be ideal for the synthesis of new chemical entities. The speed of microwave synthesis would contribute to the rapid development of novel compounds in the lead optimization stage during drug discovery process.

Abbreviations

Br: Bromine, Cl: Chloro, $^{\circ}\text{C}$: Degrees Celsius, DMF: Dimethyl formamide, F: Fluoro, h: Hour, IR: Infrared, KBr: Potassium bromide, MF: Molecular formula, Mg: Milligram, ml: Milliliters, MHz: Megahertz, MW: Microwave, NO_2 : Nitro, Nm: Nanometre, NMR: Nuclear magnetic resonance, OH: Hydroxy, OCH_3 : Methoxy, ppm: Parts per million, % : Percent, SD: Standard deviation, TLC: Thin layer chromatography, TMS: Tetramethylsilane, W: Watt.

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